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REN+HOMES - More (+) energy, less (-) emissions = a new method for positive buildings

The newly funded European Project REN+HOMES will develop a global methodology for Positive Energy Homes, residential units that produce renewable energy surplus and facilitate the transition to a climate-neutral future.

REN+HOMES- Renewable ENergy-based Positive Homes- showcase how **Positive Energy Buildings** are designed using architectural and engineering methods to **overcome energy demands**, while producing **energy surplus** using **renewable energy sources**. The goal is to create buildings that have

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a **net positive impact** on the environment and drastically **reduce greenhouse gas emissions**.

Funded by the Horizon Europe research and innovation program, this project brings together 23 partners from 8 European countries and is coordinated by the Italian [RINA Consulting SpA](#). It deploys **4 large-scale physical demonstrators** - in Austria, Spain, Estonia and Romania - introducing technical solutions exploitable for both **new construction** and **renovation**. Buildings utilising these innovative solutions produce more renewable energy throughout the year than they consume over. In addition, the consortium is actively working to develop **business models** that merge cost-effective deep-retrofitting, demand response and energy communities. REN+HOMES seeks to test, validate and share PEB solutions with potential replicability across Europe.

As technologies advance and awareness of sustainable practices grows, Positive Energy Buildings are gaining popularity as a solution to **mitigate climate change** and create a more sustainable future.

Contacts:

Project coordinator:

Margherita Fabbri, RINA Consulting S.p.A. margherita.fabbri@rina.org

Communication Manager:

Massimo Carraro, ICONS massimo.carraro@icons.it

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